

Implementing frontloading strategy in an attempt to trigger the improvement of students' vocabulary mastery

Authors : Elisabeth Regina Hoban^{1*}, Lusiana Mariyeta Balik²,
Wendelinus Oscar Janggo³

Affiliations : ^{1,2,3} English Language Education Study Program
Universitas Nusa Nipa Maumere

Correspondence : rennyhoban123@gmail.com

Abstract : In this study, the authors used the frontloading strategy to improve students' vocabulary. The main objectives of this study were to describe the implementation of the frontloading strategy in vocabulary instruction and to determine the extent to which students' vocabulary skills improved after instruction through the use of the front-loading strategy. This study is a classroom action research conducted in two cycles. Data was collected through observation, testing and interviews. Data from observations, tests and interviews from each cycle were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. The implementation of the frontloading strategy for vocabulary teaching in Class XI 3 of St. John Paul II Catholic Senior High School was carried out in two cycles. The participants in this study were 30 students. The result of this study shows that using frontloading strategy can improve students' vocabulary skills. This is evidenced by the students' test scores, which increased in each cycle, namely Cycle 1 and Cycle 2. In the first cycle, the student's average score was 50%, in the second cycle the average score was 83.33%. It can be concluded that the frontloading strategy can improve students' ability to master vocabulary and also improve teaching.

Keywords : *Vocabulary Improvement, Frontloading Strategy, Classroom Action Research*

License : This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC-BY)

Copyrights : © 2024 by Author(s)

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, the development of science and technology has become increasingly sophisticated and fast-paced. As a result, teachers with character are required to play a broad role. A nation whose people are not prepared to keep up with these changes will likely be overwhelmed by the rapid progress of science and technology. Therefore, in order to be able to participate meaningfully in the 21st century, every citizen must have the ability to respond to the demands of the times. The 21st-century learning is a transition where schools are moving away from the traditional teacher-centered approach to a student-centered one. This change is necessary for developing problem-solving, critical thinking, collaboration, and communication skills (4C skills), which are essential for future success. This capability is necessary, allowing students to adapt to the changes occurring in the community and be able to solve problems in life as individuals or social beings (Aulia, 2022). Teachers and teaching play a crucial role in supporting sustainable learning, but their primary responsibility is no longer limited to imparting knowledge to students. Education is not about filling a container, but rather igniting a spark. In the digital age of the 21st century, teachers cannot be expected to be the sole source of knowledge. Instead, their role is to inspire and guide their students as learners. Unfortunately, most teachers have not been trained to teach in this manner. Therefore, conventional teaching methods need to be modified to suit the requirements of the 21st century. In learning a variety of models can be used as an alternative, which can choose a learning model that is suitable for applied, suitable, and effective to achieve educational goals. Educators A good is a teacher who always endeavors to create the best learning conditions for their students. Teachers play a critical role in the effectiveness of training centers. Teachers determine whether there is an awareness of 21st-century skills that are critical for them to educate the lives of their students (Bozgun et al., 2023). Teachers are also required to be more creative and sensitive in creating enjoyable learning. Fun learning is also supported by a good learning model. In creating the best learning, educators choose the learning model and are required to follow what the learners will learn.

To support the learning process, students need a good and correct communication tool. Language is a suitable communication tool to facilitate every learning process activity. The language used in the 21st-century learning process is quite diverse, one of which is English. Communicating in English requires a good vocabulary and is easy to understand. Vocabulary plays an important role in human communication (Sari & Aminatun, 2021). Vocabulary is essential for written and spoken discourse in any language. As reviewing studies on vocabulary teaching, vocabulary is a large supply of words in a language. In the context of education, English vocabulary plays an important role as it is an essential component in the development of listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. Inadequate vocabulary among students can hinder their ability to express themselves effectively orally, create written works, or even understand texts. Lutfiyah et al. (2022) said that Vocabulary is a tool to determine which terms are good for communicating successfully and understanding contexts quickly, students are required to learn vocabulary well. Memorizing a large amount of vocabulary in any language can help speakers communicate with others effectively. A rich and diverse vocabulary enables individuals to express their opinions clearly, comprehend texts well, and communicate effectively in various situations (Xatamova Ziyado Gulomovna, 2023)

But in reality, in the learning process, students experience problems in mastering vocabulary, especially in English. The lack of English vocabulary makes students feel bored. In addition, many factors make students find problems in learning English vocabulary such as linguistic and non-linguistic factors. Linguistic and non-linguistic. Linguistic factors are related to language difficulties (the grammar or rules that the language uses). Non-linguistic factors

are of two types, namely internal factors (relating to one's motivation, interest, and recall of vocabulary) and external factors (relating to teaching methods, environment, or situation). (Krisnayanti & Winarta, 2021). In this case, the author looks more at the problems included in non-linguistics, especially external factors. External factors relate to learning methods, the environment, or the situation in the classroom. This problem relates to how the teacher applies effective learning methods so that it makes it easier for students to understand the material being taught. However, based on the observation made by the author during classroom learning English teachers adopt the traditional teaching mode of teacher-centered, which means teachers are present while students just listen during the class and students remember words after class. So, in the learning process, students fail to explore their own vocabulary rules. Eventually, their interest in learning will decline and vocabulary learning will become ineffective.

In addition, the author finds that limited teaching resources are also one of the factors that make learners lack vocabulary. That is, teachers teach vocabulary with English textbooks only without real and high-quality materials. English teachers in senior high schools usually use two kinds of vocabulary teaching methods. One is to explain the words and phrases in the word list one by one and give some example sentences. This type of teaching method covers a lot of large amounts of information. The example sentences given by the teacher are a little boring, and the context of the vocabulary presented is not enough for students to master the vocabulary. Besides that, the classroom atmosphere is very passive, and there are students who make noise that disturbs the classroom atmosphere becomes noisy that disrupts the teaching and learning process in the classroom. There are still other problems faced by the students themselves, which come from internal sources, including a lack of motivation to learn, lack of concentration in learning, lack of learning habits, and many other factors. All in all, there are many problems in vocabulary learning that should be solved immediately. On the other hand, it is a challenge to find interesting and effective methods to teach English vocabulary. Consequently, English teachers should be able to update better and less boring teaching concepts and methods to solve the problems in vocabulary teaching. One strategy that can be used to teach vocabulary is frontloading, also known as pre-teaching. Frontloading strategy is a strategy used to teach vocabulary by reviewing students' prior knowledge. Frontloading is a strategy that teachers use to provide guidance and reminders to students to apply the skills, strategies, and behaviors needed to be successful in the teaching and learning process in the classroom. As stated by Downs (in Kasim et al., 2023) "Frontloading vocabulary is pre-teaching vocabulary and is used as an instructional strategy to facilitate student understanding". In applying the Frontloading Strategy, students need to remember the vocabulary they have learned. Then, students list the words related to the topic given by the teacher. This strategy has several advantages, such as; it is simple, very helpful, and effective in reviewing students' vocabulary. It is a strategy that can be used in teaching vocabulary through various methods such as pictures, videos, pieces of text, and others. Thus, frontloading is a suitable strategy to help students improve their vocabulary. This strategy not only helps students improve their vocabulary knowledge but also provides interesting explanations and engaging activities to make the learning process enjoyable and informative.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This kind of topic has been examined in previous research. Ajisoko (2020) conducted the research use of Duolingo Apps to improve students' vocabulary. Putra (2023) conduct research to integrate Paper-Based Learning Mode Quizizz in EFL settings. Furthermore, Hestiana and Anita (2022) researched a good topic, namely the Role of Movie Subtitles to improve student vocabulary. This article shows that when students watch an English movie to find out the meaning through English subtitles. Furthermore, research was conducted by Tini Moge

(2022) with the aim of improving student vocabulary through Display Table Game. The last research applied is Quiroz et al. (2021). This article provides vocabulary skills through Kahoot App in Chilean classrooms.

In connection with the research, it is important to note both the similarities and differences between the previous studies and the present study. Both this study and the previous studies focus on vocabulary skills, although the objects of research are quite different. The initial study investigates students' vocabulary using Duolingo Apps, while the second study explores students' vocabulary with the Paper-Based Learning Mode Quizizz a classroom action research in an Indonesian EFL setting. Additionally, the third study analyses students' vocabulary using the Role of Movie Subtitles, and the fourth study assesses whether the Display Table Game can improve students' vocabulary. Similarly significant, the fifth research analyses the Kahoot Apps can improve students' vocabulary. On the other hand, this research focuses on Vocabulary mastery using the frontloading method in the English learning process in a secondary school, where it is utilized as a support system for learning English that is better and easier to understand and can enrich their English vocabulary skills.

METHODS

The author of this study utilized the Classroom Action Research (CAR) method to conduct the research. CAR is an action research approach in education that applies certain steps to improve the teaching and learning process, resulting in improved learning outcomes. It is an essential educational research method that educators must comprehend. According to Kemmis (in Asiyah, 2023), classroom action research is a type of reflective and communal research conducted by researchers in social situations to improve the rationale of their social practice. As a result, this approach produces changes that improve academic outcomes. Classroom Action Research (CAR) is practical research, that aims to improve deficiencies in learning practices in the classroom by taking certain actions. Classroom Action Research is directly linked to teachers' efforts to improve and enhance the quality of their classroom performance, especially during the learning process. Classroom Action Research based teaching is defined as teaching and learning by sing that the research process consists of two interrelated parts: the research process and the research results (Meesuk et al., 2020). Moreover, classroom action research is an action that teachers can use to improve teaching skills that facilitate effective student learning programs". In other words, classroom action research is a type of research conducted in the classroom to enhance the quality of the teaching and learning process. Classroom Action Research is divided into several cycles, each consisting of four stages: planning, action, observation, and reflection. As stated by Kemis and Robin action research includes four stages, namely; planning, acting, observing, and reflecting (Bhoko & Keli, 2023).

The targets of this study were 30 eleventh-grade students in St. John Paul II Maumere Catholic Senior High School. For data collection techniques, the author applied to obtain the data observation, interviews, and tests vocabulary in 2 cycles. Pre-observation was started to find out the initial ability of students' vocabulary mastery. Tests were given in the form of post-tests at the end of each cycle. In the data analysis technique, the author assessed the achievement of each student on the English test. Regarding the classical completeness of student scores, the author used a formula.

The author carried out two cycles of this research, with each cycle consisting of four meetings lasting 90 minutes each. The cycles also consist of four steps: planning, implementation of observation actions, and reflection. The research was based on the assumption that the teaching and learning process was not optimal during the first cycle due to the improper application of the frontloading technique. In the second cycle, the author

optimized the frontloading strategy method, resulting in students becoming active and interested in solving the given problems.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Pre-cycle

During the orientation period of the school environment the author observed the process of teaching and learning English in the classroom then interviewed teachers and students about how the experience of learning English and how the atmosphere during English learning and the use of media carried out or applied by the teacher the orientation. Before starting the English learning cycle, the author conducted an observation of the student's interaction and gave them a pre-test to evaluate their English proficiency and identify existing problems, particularly in their vocabulary ability. The observation showed that the students in class XI 3 were less enthusiastic about learning English. They perceived the learning process in class as boring and confusing, and they struggled to understand the vocabulary taught.

During an interview with an English teacher, it was found that most students struggled with English because of a lack of interest difficulties with the subject, and lack of vocabulary mastery in the process of learning English. The teacher that students did not participate well in the classroom due to a lack of mastery of vocabulary which made them feel difficult and quickly bored. Similarly, student interviews revealed that they found it difficult to learn English and difficult to interpret vocabulary in English or Indonesian. Besides, students have less vocabulary knowledge which makes it difficult to complete the exercise as well as answer questions. As a result, the atmosphere in the classroom became less enjoyable.

To evaluate students' English language skills, the author performs pre-test vocabulary. The pre-test results for 31 October 2023 of Class XI 3 consisting of 30 students, showed that only eight students achieved the skill criteria, with 26.6% of them achieving graduation scores. The 26.6% result was obtained from the number of students who scored high scores, multiplied by 100%, divided by the number of students, and then produced by 26.6%. Based on observations and interviews, it seems impossible to encourage students to work harder. Instead, they need a more interesting and understandable learning approach. After examining the students' pre-test results, the author conducted cycle 1. This cycle involves the use of frontloading methods to improve vocabulary skills in students.

Cycle I

In this stage, the author looks at the implementation of the action and the results of the observation. Then the author made a way to modify the action by using the Frontloading strategy. This aims to give students time and space to define the English words they have learned and remember them easily. Regarding this stage, the author chose the right material based on the syllabus and the author compiled it into a lesson plan. The author prepared tests and instruments to measure student achievement as data collection. The author prepared a teacher activity observation sheet that would be filled in by the observer, while the student activity observation sheet was filled in by the author. In this cycle, the author planned activities to describe synonyms as the topic in the learning process that the students would learn. Students are given motivation or stimulation to focus on the material topic by looking at and observing the pictures given to students. The text already given is read by the author and followed by the student. After that, the author explores the student's knowledge of the given text through several elective questions related to the places described on the board. Two cycles, each lasting 90 minutes, were to be conducted as part of this research. In addition, some of the students showed insufficient motivation and confidence when voicing and explaining about the pictures in front

of the board. The students also struggled to articulate their thoughts due to their limited vocabulary and also the author found that in the first cycle meeting using the frontloading strategy, some students just sat on their chairs and looked at the pictures in front of the class because they did not understand the meaning this means that they did not understand the meaning of the vocabulary, so the lack of vocabulary in the learning process as well as less optimal especially in answering questions. Based on the observation of vocabulary test results, the average test result that passed the Criteria of Success was 50%. The 50% result was obtained from 15 students who scored a high score, multiplied by 100%, divided by the number of 30 students, and then got the result by 50%. Observing and analyzing the results of this cycle, the author thought to redesign the strategies used to improve vocabulary skills in the next cycle.

With regard to the reflection stage, there are several areas for improvement identified by the authors. First, it is important to improve teaching techniques to create a positive learning environment that is more enjoyable at the beginning of the test. Second, it is important for the researcher to provide opportunities for students to ask questions and clarify their learning objectives. Third, the author recommends students to use dictionaries, online or offline. Finally, a clear explanation of the process of applying the Frontloading method is essential. Therefore, based on the analysis of students' average scores and observations collected during the Cycle I post-test held on 02 November 2023, the researcher identified the need to conduct further action research in Cycle II.

Cycle II

In this case, the author prepared the material, research time, and assignments in cycle 2 to compare student results whether they had improved or not. The demands of this cycle are the author must be more creative in some materials in order to make the class fun. The author must do this when the teaching and learning process takes place. The author chooses the topic then the students will identify the vocabulary given by the author in front of the class. The author asked the students to make some groups. Before making groups, the author told students to sway Charlie Bear Bada Boop then the author told students to find friends in 1 group. After that, the author pasted several pictures related to the topic to be tested in front of the class. Then the author conveyed the rules about the frontloading strategy and asked students who did not understand the frontloading learning strategy. Students are given motivation or stimulation to focus on the topic of the material by observing the pictures given to them students. The author provides English vocabulary clues if students have difficulty finding the vocabulary in the picture. The author gave the students time to discuss with their groups and identify the vocabulary in the pictures. After that, students mentioned and wrote on the board the vocabulary they saw from each picture. Then, the author revised and added the vocabulary they found. The author and students had a question and answer session about the pictures given. The author gave the text to the students, the text was read by the author and followed by the students. After that, the author explored the students' knowledge of the text given through question-and-answer activities. At the end of cycle 2, the author gave a test as an instrument to students to find out if there was an increase in students' vocabulary mastery. This can be seen from the achievement of the scores they achieved in cycle 2. The author gave 20 multiple-choice questions. The author instructed the students to answer the questions correctly according to the picture that had been explained. During the learning process using the Frontloading Strategy method, students are more active in learning vocabulary. Students are more active in finding new vocabulary by using online English dictionaries.

Based on the results of the vocabulary mastery post-test in the second cycle, the average score of vocabulary mastery was 83.33 %, and students who passed the success. The 83,33% result was obtained from 25 students who scored a high score, multiplied by 100%, divided by the number of 30 students, and then got the result by 83,33%. This means that there were 17% who did not pass the success of criteria. The criteria of success were met by the second cycle post-test held on 04 November 2023. The results also showed that the second cycle had met the success criteria on the given research instrument. The author and the English teacher at the school decided to stop the class action research because it had successfully improved students' vocabulary skills through the Frontloading Strategy, and it was in accordance with the plan previously discussed by the author and the teacher.

DISCUSSION

Teaching vocabulary acquisition using frontloading strategy to students of class XI 3 of Santo Yohanes Paulus II Catholic High School Maumere. Frontloading strategy refers to an approach where most of the information or learning materials are given at the beginning of the learning process. It aims to increase the understanding of the material by the students. The pre-test results as many as 26.6% (8 students) got high scores while some students showed that students' initial understanding of the material was still low. Therefore, the author plans to apply the relevant frontloading strategy to improve learning effectiveness.

Frontloading can be an effective solution to overcome students' comprehension weaknesses. Taking into account the low pre-test results, frontloading strategy was applied in the learning process. The learning materials are organized in such a way that key information is presented at the beginning of the lesson. This can help students build a strong knowledge base from the beginning so that it can help them better understand more complex concepts. Based on interviews with 30 students, it is known that the Pre-test score is 26.6% of 8 students who have scores above the completeness criteria. Whereas in Post test 1 it is known that 50% or 15 students scored above the completeness criteria and in cycle 2 it is known that 83.33% where there are 25 students who managed to get a score according to the completeness criteria.

After the implementation of frontloading, the first post-test was conducted which showed a significant improvement in students' understanding. The post-test 1 result of 50% shows that the frontloading strategy has a positive impact on students' ability to understand the material. Although the first cycle showed improvement, this cycle cannot be said to be successful. To overcome this problem, the educator-author started the lesson with an interesting introduction to attract students' interest in learning. They also clarified the course content in a clear and efficient manner to foster a productive classroom environment and enable students to ask questions and achieve learning objectives through the use of various media. This approach motivates students to develop their English communication skills, particularly in expressing their viewpoints and ideas. Providing encouragement and positive views to motivate students to be more actively involved. After that, the researcher felt satisfied because the effort to improve student's vocabulary skills had been realized. This was shown by the significant results in cycle II, where the class average increased to 83.33%. Throughout the teaching and learning activities, especially during the implementation of the cycle, the author who acted as a teacher consistently provided clear and interesting explanations while providing feedback on students' progress and deep motivation. The style used was not too formal to ensure optimal understanding. All of it was delivered in English but on the one hand, the author used Indonesian, where gradually the author provided experience so that students were accustomed to hearing conversations, or expressions of sentences in English but the author also balanced it with the situation of the students. The author also provides opportunities for students to guess"

and "translate meaning based on their ability through the English dictionary. Sometimes the author often uses body movements to sharpen students' brains. In relation to that, the results of interviews, questionnaires, and observation sheets also proved the high level of students' involvement, engagement, and cohesiveness in the vocabulary learning process using the frontloading method. This can be seen from the results of the learning process. English teachers appreciated the use of this frontloading method in teaching and learning activities. They stated that it is an easy way to attract students' interest in learning English because the researcher used interesting pictures that can foster students' imagination. In addition, pictures can be attractive to students. Images with various colors are more attractive and can arouse interest and attention. Pictures are the media used by the author when conducting research. The use of learning media can help children understand the learning material provided. In addition, educational media can also increase children's motivation and interest. Learning media can also help develop all aspects of students' or children's development (Utami et al., 2021)

The author only acted as a facilitator providing guidance, while the students performed all tasks independently. Some students who were initially silent and did not understand the meaning of the vocabulary have also been able to be active, although they still look shy to express the meaning of the pictures on the board. Their confidence is slowly increasing towards the abilities that students are expected to achieve. Based on the author's observation, students were seen helping each other to explain the pictures on the board. This increased the liveliness of the learning environment, although it was noisier. However, the noise was not disruptive but rather created a good atmosphere so that other students felt that they were not left behind.

Each lesson in the cycle ended with students feeling one step closer to their goal. The success of improving their English vocabulary through the frontloading method was aided by the author's strategic adjustments. This required the author to master the subject matter well, be proficient in technology, and accommodate the learning environment to the students' needs. The author provided assessment methods to measure students' progress through exercises, and tests. Finally, it can be concluded that the use of frontloading method can improve vocabulary proficiency in students.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of the Frontloading strategy learning model in an effort to improve student's vocabulary mastery has been carried out in accordance with the implementation plan. students' vocabulary mastery has been carried out in accordance with the prepared lesson plan lesson plan that was prepared. The frontloading strategy learning process was carried out in two cycles, where each cycle consists of four stages, namely: planning stage, implementation stage, observation stage, and reflection stage.

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, it can be concluded that the frontloading strategy learning model can improve students' vocabulary acquisition seen from cycle 1 by 50% and in cycle 2 by 83.33%, this means that the increase from cycle 1 to 2 is successful because of a good increase. So, it can be concluded that the application of the frontloading strategy can improve the vocabulary acquisition of students in class XI 3 of St. John Paul II Catholic Senior High School Maumere.

In addition, Therefore, each cycle can improve students' vocabulary mastery after using the Frontloading strategy, teaching and learning process by using the Frontloading strategy; this has an impact on students' students' motivation for learning, students are more active, and can foster students' self-confidence. Frontloading strategy can improve students' vocabulary mastery. This can be observed in students who remain engaged and attentive during

the learning process. The author also concluded that the frontloading strategy can increase the understanding of unfamiliar words in each cycle. This means that students' vocabulary acquisition by using the frontloading strategy has improved a lot and the author succeeded in teaching vocabulary mastery using the frontloading strategy. Lastly, it is recommended that future authors use the results of this study as a reference and comparison when researching teaching vocabulary using the frontloading strategy or other appropriate techniques. They should also review and evaluate the findings of this study and compare them with other research methods.

REFERENCES

- Ajisoko, P. (2020). The use of duolingo apps to improve English vocabulary learning. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 15(7), 149–155. <https://doi.org/10.3991/IJET.V15I07.13229>
- Asiyah, T. (2023). *Peningkatan Keterampilan Berbicara Bahasa Indonesia dengan Penerapan Model Pembelajaran Deep Dialogue Melalui Pendekatan Saintifik (PTK di kelas III MI An-Nahwa Kec. Taktakan Kota Serang)*. UIN Sultan Maulana Hasanuddin Banten.
- Aulia, E. (2022). Effects of 21st Century Learning on the Development of Critical Thinking, Creativity, Communication, and Collaboration Skills. *Journal of Nonformal Education*, 8(1), 46–53.
- Bhoko, M. L., & Keli, E. W. (2023). IMPROVING STUDENTS SPEAKING SKILLS THROUGH DEBATE STRATEGY. *KLAUSA (Kajian Linguistik, Pembelajaran Bahasa, Dan Sastra)*, 7(1), 90–99.
- Bozgun, K., Ozaskin-Arslan, A. G., & Ulucinar-Sagir, S. (2023). COVID-19 and Distance Education: Evaluation in the Context of Twenty-first Century Skills. *Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 32(3), 417–428. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-022-00663-4>
- Hestiana, M., & Anita, A. (2022). The Role of Movie Subtitles To Improve Students' Vocabulary. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning*, 3(1), 46–53. <https://doi.org/10.33365/jeltl.v3i1.1715>
- Kasim, N. P., Talib, R. R., & Mestari, S. A. (2023). Enriching Students' Vocabulary by Using Frontloading Strategy. *Research Review: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin*, 2(2), 253–264.
- Krisnayanti, N. P. A., & Winarta, I. B. G. N. (2021). The problems of learning english vocabulary in harapan senior high school. *Journal of Language and Applied Linguistics*, 2(2), 201–207. <https://doi.org/10.22334/traverse.v2i2.46>
- Lutfiyah, N., Nuraeningsih, N., & Rusiana, R. (2022). The Obstacles in Learning Vocabulary of Efl Students. *Prominent*, 5(2), 114–125. <https://doi.org/10.24176/pro.v5i2.8257>
- Meesuk, P., Sramoon, B., & Wongrugsa, A. (2020). Classroom action research-based instruction: The sustainable teacher professional development strategy. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability*, 22(1), 98–110.
- Putra, R. W. P. (2023). Improving Students' Vocabulary Through Paper-Mode Quizizz: A Classroom Action Research in Indonesian EFL setting. *English Learning Innovation*, 4(1), 22–31. <https://doi.org/10.22219/englie.v4i1.24832>
- Quiroz, M. F., Gutiérrez, R., Rocha, F., Valenzuela, M. P., & Vilches, C. (2021). Improving English Vocabulary Learning Through Kahoot!: A Quasi-Experimental High School Experience. *Teaching English with Technology*, 21(2), 3–13.
- Sari, S. N., & Aminatun, D. (2021). Students' Perception on the Use of English Movies To Improve Vocabulary Mastery. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning*, 2(1), 16–22. <https://doi.org/10.33365/jeltl.v2i1.757>

- Tini Moge. (2022). Improving Students' Vocabulary Through Display Table Game. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Sastra Inggris*, 2(3), 172–184.
<https://doi.org/10.55606/jupensi.v2i3.979>
- Utami, F., Rukiyah, Andika, W. D., & Sumarni, S. (2021). *Introduction to Sea Animals With Augmented Reality Based Flashcard for Early Childhood*. 513, 215–220.
<https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.201230.108>
- Xatamova Ziyado Gulomovna, K. U. (2023). Effective Methods To Increase Vocabulary in English As a second Language. *Journal of Universal Science Research*.